

COGNITIVE ANALYSIS AS AN APPROACH TO THE LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6465137>

Annotation. The article is managed the issues of examination of language, which are the formal, the mental, and the applied. Mental methodology is worried about the designs in which and the cycles by which applied content is coordinated in language, or then again, all in all, how language structures applied content. What's more, mental phonetics concentrates on how language constructions such essential applied classifications as those of room and time, scenes and occasions, elements and properties, movement and area, power and causation.

Keywords: cognitive, linguistics, approach, analysis, language, patterns, lexical structure, conceptual content, grammatical means.

Introduction. Mental etymology showed up inside a system of ways to deal with the examination of language, which are the formal, the mental, and the theoretical. The conventional methodology addresses the phonetic examples, preoccupied away from any related importance. Along these lines, this approach incorporates the investigation of morphological, syntactic, lexical construction. Conventional generative language has focused itself inside this methodology. The mental methodology takes a gander at language according to the viewpoint of general mental frameworks; inside this methodology language is inspected according to the viewpoint of insight, memory, consideration, and thinking. The principle focus of the calculated methodology is to think about the worldwide arrangement of schematic structures with which language sorts out applied content that it communicates. Mental methodology is worried about the examples in which and the cycles by which theoretical substance is coordinated in language, or, at the end of the day, how language structures applied content. Mental semantics concentrates on how language constructions such fundamental calculated classifications as those of reality, scenes and occasions, substances and properties, movement and area, power and causation. It considers the semantic design of morphological and lexical structures as well as that of syntactic examples. Mental semantics thinks about language as a mental framework, which alongside other mental frameworks, for example, insight,

consideration, thinking, influence, memory, and engine control involves human discernment. In this regard language seems to have a primary properties normal to other mental frameworks.^[1]

As one can see that while talking about syntactic relations between words we notice the terms coordination, subjection, predication, understanding and government. It appears to be that it is vital to separate the initial three terms (coordination, subjection and predication) from the terms arrangement and government, in light of the fact that the initial three terms characterize the kinds of grammatical relations from the outlook of reliance of the parts while the subsequent ones characterize the syntactic relations according to the perspective of the correspondence of the syntactic types of their parts. Arrangement and government manages as it were subjection and doesn't have anything to do with practical dexterity and predication. Other than understanding also, government there is another sort of grammatical relations which might be called collocation when head and assistant words are associated with one another not by formal syntactic means. The syntactic design of language involves two significant parts - morphology and linguistic structure. The two regions are clearly related and together they establish the investigation of language. Morphology manages paradigmatic and syntagmatic properties of morphological units - morphemes and words. It is worried about the inside construction of words and their relationship to different words and word structures inside the worldview. It studies morphological classes and their acknowledgment. Linguistic structure, then again, manages how words are joined. It is worried about the outer elements of words and their relationship to different words inside the straightly requested units - word-gatherings, sentences and messages. Grammar concentrates on the manner by which the units furthermore, their implications are joined. It likewise manages idiosyncrasies of syntactic units, their conduct in various settings. Syntactic units might be dissected according to various perspectives, and likewise, unique syntactic speculations exist. In this manner, the fundamental units of linguistic structure, expressions and sentences, enter the arrangement of language by their syntactic examples. Syntactic examples are explained in syntagmatic and paradigmatic designing. An expression is a nominative syntactic unit. The term 'express' can be utilized just alluding to such gatherings of words that contain no less than two notional words shaping semantic and syntactic entirety. Two and

¹ Бенвенист Э. Общая лингвистика. Москва: Прогресс, 1974. 447 с.

more notional words can shape an expression through hypotaxis, or subjection. As indicated by the underlying methodology, hypotaxis joins components of various positions that could be called the principle and ward components, or the head and the extra individually, e.g.: magnificent climate. One of the parts rules over the other(s) and subordinates it (them) what concerns both structure and game plan.

Notwithstanding, the way that customary primary methodology is as yet famous, it needs improvement as mental part of expression investigation can give further comprehension of expression development standards. The motivation behind this article is to consider phrases in English according to the perspective of their applied substance, for example impression of linguistic ideas in an expression. Linguistic ideas are considered as mental implications that are framed in cognizance of an individual making non-discrete units, still up in the air by language experience to show associations and different attributes of various objects. To lead the examination we utilize semantic cognitive technique pointed toward deciding the primary and subordinate components of the expression and their qualities, their similarity as well as mental translation and demonstrating Through ceaseless inspecting approach, 1000 instances of expressions from unconstrained everyday discourse were chosen. Idea demonstrating is somewhat fundamental these days not just what concerns lexical units that were profoundly explored by various analysts yet punctuation units also. Despite the fact that state parts keep their lexical it is no to mean there unambiguous consistence among syntactic and semantic levels, which causes us to presume that not person parts however the entire word mix as well as interrelation of the components included and their capacity to reflect extralinguistic thoughts ought to be liable to mental investigation. A grammatically addressed idea fills in as a theoretical substrate by implication showing the relationship between extralinguistic substances and semantic signs. This association is conceivable because of the way that such an idea incorporates the most summed up data about relationship between the objective elements in the plan "subject - activity - object of an activity", and every part of the applied conspire, in its turn, is projected over the construction of the sentence. A propositional structure, or a suggestion, is a model of calculated association for our information, a psychological design that mirrors the normal circumstance and the idea of its members' associations. Suggestion design decides decision of syntactic structures.^[2] An expression is a suggestion

² Langacker R.W. Cognitive Grammar. A Basic Introduction. Oxford: OxfordUniversity

in its packed structure, as one of the fundamental contentions of the suggestion: either a subject or a predicate is missing. Cf.: the young lady remaining at the window and The young lady is remaining at the window. I'm more OK with Dad in light of his great driving and I'm more OK with Dad since he drives without a hitch.

Considering another rule, semantic substance of the word, we could recognize two sorts of word implications: absolute and relative. Words with absolute (non-relative) significance needn't bother with their importance to be finished. They can be appropriated in a sentence with the assistance of different words, however not really: another dress, a table made of wood, and so on. Relative words need to have their significance finished: An uncle came in. Coherently emerges the question: Whose uncle? Relative/non-relative kind of a word is viewed as a central constitutive component to describe various words as far as their projections in data stream association. All things considered, a few words could communicate either relative or absolute significance, contingent upon the specific situation. Cf.: wooden dividers, for example dividers made of wood; wooden grin, for example an blank grin. Considering the components making the expression it is important to take note of that most heads of word blends are communicated by an action word (or its non limited structures) or a thing. Foundation ideas common for action words or their non-limited structures could indicate activity: to go* to the establishment; process: to dry* quickly; some state: to be* dry; both activity and interaction: to dry* the wood, where the article is changed, and some specialist playing out this activity could be referenced, e.g.: Someone dried the wood (* marks the head). Adding the second reliant component to the fundamental verb component presents new reasonable implications as follows: a) limitation, alluding to the immediate subject area: to be at the college; the spot the subject methodologies: to go to the college; the spot the subject methodologies having no explicit reason to remain there: to go towards the theater, or having particular reason at the top of the priority list like remaining close by: to go to the window, to rush to the youngster, developments in space: to walk along the street. Confinement of static subjects or articles is decided connecting with their spacial area: to be in the table, to be on the table; b) direction for an individual or an article: gave my sibling a book; c) transient direction: come at 5 o'clock; d) center around the means or the method for making a move: is composed with a pen; e) activity

qualities: to run rapidly, where explicit attributes of an activity are referenced; to examine with the instructor, where joint person of an activity is underscored.

Conclusion. To summarize, mental examination of an expression could serve to decide its particular importance and to figure out how the language reflects extralinguistic reality and associations, or relations between its items. The uncovered mental standards as well as their more profound impact over state development ought to be investigated further utilizing tests from different sorts of discourse in current English. As per the exploration directed, the sort of an expression also, attributes of its parts rely upon a few measures: first, the goal of a speaker, foundation information, importance of the data delivered, second, language developments accessible for communicating mental relations. Any shift in the course of applied relations is reflected in run of the mill significance of this development and the decision of lexical units that comprise the sentence.

REFERENCES

1. Бенвенист Э. Общая лингвистика. Москва: Прогресс, 1974. 447 с.
2. Langacker R.W. Cognitive Grammar. A Basic Introduction. Oxford: OxfordUniversity Press, 2008.562 p.
3. Taylor J.K. Cognitive Grammar. Oxford, 2002.
4. Махмудов Н., Нурмонов А. Ўзбек тилининг назарий грамматикаси. Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1995. 232 б.
5. Арутюнова Н.Д. Предложение и его смысл. Логико-семантические проблемы / Н.Д. Арутюнова. – М., 1976. – 383 с.
6. Болдырев Н.Н. Когнитивная семантика: Курс лекций по английской филологии / Н.Н. Болдырев. – Тамбов: Изд-во Тамбов. ун-та, 2000. – 123 с.
7. Болдырев Н.Н. Репрезентация языковых и неязыковых знаний синтаксическими средствами / Н.Н. Болдырев, Л.А. Фурс // Филологические науки. – 2004. – № 3. – С. 67–74.
8. Гайсина Р.М. Лексико-семантическое поле глаголов отношения в современном русском языке / Р.М. Гайсина. – Саратов: Изд-во Саратов. гос. ун-та, 1981. – 195 с.
9. Теньер Л. Основы структурного синтаксиса / Л. Теньер. – М.: Прогресс, 1988. – 656 с.
10. A Corpus of English Conversation. – L.: Gleerup, 1980. – 893 p.
11. Evans V. Cognitive Linguistics: An Introduction / V. Evans, M. Green. – Routledge, 2006. – 830 p.
12. Grice H.P. Logic and Conversation / H.P. Grice // Syntax and Semantics. Vol. 3: Speech Acts. – N.Y.: Academic Press, 1975. – P. 41- 58.
13. Langacker R.W. Foundations of Cognitive Grammar: Vol.1: Theoretical Prerequisites / R.W Langacker. – Stanford: Stanford UP, 1987. – 516 p.